

MANAGEMENT OF WORK ASSISTANCE FOR INMATES IN CULTIVATING EMPOWERMENT AND INDEPENDENCE (A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY IN FEMALE PENITENTIARY CLASS IIA BANDUNG)

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Abstract

The guidance program in Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung has two programs, i.e., personality and independence. Independence guidance is conducted via job guidance programs focused on developing the inmates' abilities and skills, expected to contribute to workforce distribution and suppress the unemployment rate of released inmates. The study aimed to discover the job guidance management at the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung. The study method was descriptive research with a qualitative approach by collecting data through observation and interviews. The study concluded that the work assistance management for inmates in cultivating empowerment and independence has succeeded since it offers positive impacts for inmates and reaches the target. The authors recommend that the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung use this study as a reference to further develop job guidance management. Future studies can refer to this study by focusing on the problems studied and enriching literature study and data completion.

Keywords: Guidance, Independence, Work Assistance.

INTRODUCTION

Norms are specific rules to be executed and complied with by all society members in their lives. However, many people violate such rules and commit crimes currently. Over time, crimes committed by females, including corruption, murder, fraud, and robbery, become more prominent. The high rate of crimes is driven by the desire to increase one's standard of living from emotional, personal, financial, and negative external factors. Those proven conduct violations must be punished following the penalties imposed. Each criminal or inmate must serve their time in a penitentiary. The Regulation of the Minister of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia No. 6 of 2013 Chapter I Article 1 Paragraph 1 states that "penitentiary (laps) are locations where inmate training is running. Penitentiaries are essential in performing technical activities under the Director General of Corrections, Ministry of Law and Human Rights. Penitentiaries are usually occupied by those receiving inmates, convicts, or inmates."

Inmates are a part of the Indonesian population with the right to receive guidance in education and training. Syamsuddin (1997:2) explained that "a person who commits crime or law violation includes in a deviant action. The guidance for inmates in correctional facilities is not

merely a problem for themselves, but also a social problem to be handled based on applicable social regulations.”

The problems ensnaring female criminals must be resolved with the help of empowerment. Empowerment grants them skills in managing the values inherent in human life, individually and in groups, providing independence aligned with their desires. Kuncoro (2016:46) stated, “Empowerment is an activity step where an individual can develop knowledge, skills, and abilities to achieve goals and offer something to society to increase the value of life, society, groups, and individuals.”

Based on the Regulation of the Government of the Republic of Indonesia Number 31 of 1999, Chapter 1, Article 1 Paragraph 1, “Guidance can improve the quality of devotion to the Almighty, intellectual, behavior and attitude, physical and spiritual health, professionalism of inmates, and correctional students.” The guidance program aims to ease the lives of released inmates. This guidance can transform the mindset and personality of inmates, which has long been considered negative by the public, into a better mindset following typical life norms.

The process of guiding inmates is a critical educational step for the public. Crimes committed by inmates disrupt the comfort and social order before and after the detaining. This issue requires special concern from all parties involved in social order.

The guidance program in a Penitentiary commonly refers to two divisions, i.e., personality and independence. Personality guidance is a step to guide inmates by emphasizing their spiritual and mental aspects. Meanwhile, independence guidance emphasizes developing their abilities and skills.

The Penitentiary should help fund the solution for released inmates to acquire decent work opportunities. This training will contribute to workforce distribution and suppress the unemployment rate and recidivism of inmates post-release.

Pool & Sewell (2007:279-280) asserted that “a condition where released inmates are ready to work is urgently required. Hence, various supports are necessary, such as intelligence, knowledge, good character, critical thinking, and skills suitable to their interests to be comfortable in their work environment and be successful.”

From the problem above, the researchers took an interest in discovering and explaining the work assistance management for inmates in cultivating empowerment and independence in the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung. The study aims to discover:

1. Steps of the job guidance program in Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung.
2. Implementation of the job guidance program in Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung.
3. Obstacles in the job guidance program held.
4. Impacts of the job guidance program followed by inmates.
5. Evaluation of the job guidance program held.

RESEARCH METHODS

The study is descriptive research. According to Sugiyono (2012:13), “descriptive research is conducted to observe the individual variable score, whether one or more variables (independent) by excluding a comparison or correlating them to other variables.” This study method aimed to produce accurately described, trusted, actual, factual, and coherent data. Furthermore, the study approach was qualitative.

Data in this study were acquired directly from the field, commonly called primary data. Furthermore, the study also employed secondary data sources from various articles and news. The subject in research was the parties directly involving themselves and understanding the work assistance management for inmates in cultivating empowerment and independence, i.e., Head of Work Activities Section, Head of Job Guidance Subsidy and Management of Work Results, and Community Inmates. Data collection comprised three steps based on a study by Sugiyono (2010:137): getting in, getting along, and logging the data. After collecting all the data, data analysis and interpretation were performed by reducing, selecting, explaining, and concluding the data using domain analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. General Condition

The Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung was established to guide female inmates as mentioned by Act No. 12 of 1995 on Corrections. Article 12 states, “In the context of inmate guidance in penitentiaries, classification is based on age, gender, length of sentence imposed, type of crime, and other criteria under the guidance needs and development.” Meanwhile, Article 2 states, “The guidance for female inmates in penitentiaries is carried out in Female Penitentiaries.” Female Penitentiary Bandung was built based on the Decree of the Minister of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia Number: M.03-PR.07.03 of 2007 dated 23 February 2007 on the Establishment of Female Penitentiaries in Palembang, Bandar Lampung, Bandung, and Sungguminasa. Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung was established on 19 November 2007 but first operated on 1 February 2008, marked by accepting female penitentiaries transferred from Penitentiary Class IIA Banceuy Bandung. Based on the Decree of the Minister of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia Number M.HH-09.OT.01.01 of 2016 dated 15 July 2016 on Changes in the Nomenclature of Women’s Penitentiary to become Female Penitentiary. Hence, the Women’s Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung became Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung.

Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung stands on land extending to 9,129.90 M², with a building of 4,064.60 M² equipped with five housing blocks and 48 rooms. Following a Circular Letter from the Director General of Corrections, each inmate must have 5.4 m/person movement space. Thus, the occupancy capacity of the Female Penitentiary Bandung is 227 inmates. Meanwhile, according to the bed area of 2 m/person, the capacity is 229 inmates. According to the Regulation of the Minister of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia Number: M.HH-05.OT.01.01 of 2011 on Amendments to the Decree of the Minister

of Justice Number: M.01-PR.07.03 of 1985 on the Organization and Work Procedures of Correctional Institutions, the Female Penitentiary Bandung is included in the Class IIA classification. According to existing data, the number of inmates in the Female Penitentiary Bandung up to April 2024 was 394.

2. Main Duties and Functions

The Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung under the leadership of the Head of the Penitentiary, Mrs. Tri Winarsih, has a role in providing correctional assignments to all female inmates/students. Community service aims to guide people in correctional institutions according to systems, institutions, and training methods as the final aspect of criminal sentences based on criminal justice regulations. Meanwhile, the uses of correctional institutions include:

- a. Provide guidance for inmates
- b. Provide suggestions, prepare facilities, and manage work results
- c. Provide consultation in social and spiritual aspects for inmates
- d. Organize maintenance of order and security in prisons
- e. Carry out administrative and household interests

According to the Regulation of the Minister of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia Number: M.HH-05.OT.01.01 of 2011 on Amendments to the Decree of the Minister of Justice Number: M.01-PR.07.03 of 1985 on Organization and Work Procedures of Correctional Institutions, the job descriptions in the Women's Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung are as follows:

a. Head of Penitentiary

Coordinate and supervise all activities at the Women's Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung

b. Administration Subdivision

Carry out the administrative and household interests of the penitentiary. This subdivision includes:

1) Employment and Financial Affairs

Conduct employment and financial interests. Employment Affairs relates to the regulation implementation for employees, including proposals for employee formation, CPNS, Civil Servant, promotion, KGB, position, employee leave, disciplinary punishments, employee welfare, pensions, and others. Meanwhile, financial affairs relate to budget management, financial reporting administration, and budget proposals.

2) General Affairs

Conduct correspondence needs and manage infrastructure and household facilities.

c. Inmate/Student Guidance Section

Guide the inmates in the penitentiary. This section includes:

1) Registration Subsection

Record inmates or students, create statistics, record dactyloscopy fingerprints, perform documentation, reporting, and evaluation.

2) Correctional Guidance and Treatment Subsection

Guide and conduct spiritual counseling, provide physical training, personal character, intellectual knowledge development, guidance steps (Assimilation, CB, CMB, PB), and treatment such as food, drink, and healthcare to inmates.

d. Work Activity Section

Assist in work, help prepare work facilities, and manage work results. This section includes:

- 1) Work Assistance and Work Result Management Subsection with the role of showing and assisting work training for inmates/students and managing work results.
- 2) Work Facilities Subsection with the role of preparing work facilities for work assistance for inmates.

e. Security Administration and Code of Conduct Section

Create rules on list of duties of the security forces, use of security facilities, division of duties of the security forces, obtain daily reports and minutes from the security units assigned to prepare reports over time in the security and order enforcement division. This section includes:

1) Security Subsection

Create rules on the list of duties of the security forces, use of security facilities, and division of duties of the security forces.

2) Report and Code of Conduct Subsection

Acquire daily reports and minutes from the security units assigned to prepare reports over time in the security and order enforcement division.

f. Prison Security Unit (KPLP)

The Prison Security Unit (KPLP) is led by a Head that supervises prison security officers. The Head of the Prison Security Unit has direct responsibility to the Head of the Prison. KPLP has a role in overseeing the implementation of security and order in prisons, including organizing security and supervising inmates, maintaining security and order, overseeing the reception, placement, and release of inmates, checking various violations in security, and creating daily reports and minutes of security program implementation.

As of April 2024, the total number of staff at the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung is 89 people, comprising 14 Structural Officials, Technical Functional Positions (doctor: 1 person, dentist: 1 person, midwife: 2 people, and nurse: 4 people), 28 Security Team, 26 General Functional Positions, and 3 CPNS (potential civil servants).

3. Organizational Structure

4. Job guidance Management

The role and use of the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung is providing guidance for inmates. The guidance carried out at the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung is divided into two, i.e., personality and independence. The goal of cultivating personality is to produce a figure with strength and solidity in producing work in prison and post-release. This guidance is expected to allow inmates be prepared to carry out their lives after being released. The following is included in the personality development:

- a. Religious Awareness (Spirituality)
- b. Intellectual and Legal Counseling
- c. Physical
- d. Art
- e. National Awareness

Meanwhile, independence guidance is expected to create a figure with independence who can rely on themselves since they have excellent abilities or skills to conduct their life in public and can create jobs after being released. Therefore, job guidance activities are based on the rules and use of the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung. The job guidance activities have been conducted since the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung was established.

Under the leadership of Mrs. Whittier sundari as the head of word activity section, work good in activities are divided into 3 types, i.e., manufacturer, service, and agribusiness which are further divided into several job posts:

1. Sewing activities
2. Patchwork activities
3. Resin activities
4. Bakery activities
5. Catering activities
6. Florist activities
7. Salon activities
8. Reflection activities
9. Facial activities
10. Gardening activities
11. Hydroponic activities
12. Fishery activities

Each inmate must join job guidance activities, except for those who are elderlies and half serious health issues, which do not have to join any job guidance activities. The inmates are free to select job guidance activities according to their interest and talents.

The guidance is divided into 3 stages: initial, advance, and final. Initial guidance is appointed for and executed after a person has the inmate status until a third of her serving time. The first advance stage is conducted after the end of the initial guidance stage until half of her serving time. Meanwhile, the second advance stage is conducted after the end of the first advance stage until two-third of her serving time.

In job guidance activities, there are steps to be performed by every inmate, i.e., registration, having completed 1/3 of the serving time, and the TPP trial or correctional observer team trial. The total number of inmates participating in job posts until April 2024 was 166 people. The details of the inmates at each job post are as follows:

Month	Number of Inmates	Number of Inmates at Each Job post										
		Sewing	Patchwork	Painting	Screen Printing	Salon	Facial	Bakery	Catering	Park	Gardening	Fishery
Januari	422	7	14	6	2	5	1	9	7	20	20	10
February	405	9	14	6	2	5	1	9	7	20	20	10
March	400	7	14	6	1	5	1	9	7	20	20	10
April	394	7	14	6	1	5	1	9	7	15	50	6

The job guidance activities held are a method of guiding and empowering inmates at the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung. The job guidance training aims to empower, grow, develop, and increase the potential within the inmates and develop themselves. Therefore, when they are released, they can re-socialize with the surrounding community.

Planning in carrying out job guidance development is critical to allow job guidance development implementation achieving the objectives. The job guidance is planned by correctional officers. The process is carried out by determining the interests and talents of the inmates. At the initial stage of the activity, the inmates are identified and taking an assessment to discover their interests and talents. This identification and assessment activity is essential to direct the program and achieve the desired results. Moreover, the inmates can take part in the existing training program, followed by joining job guidance activities matching their interests and talents.

The job guidance activities is carried out every Monday - Friday from 08.00 to 12.00. Based on the observation results, job guidance activities are quite conducive and carried out well. Each inmate are aware and responsible in taking part in the job guidance activities selected. In its implementation, job guidance activities involving tutors are flexible, since guidance in job guidance activities is not merely centered on existing tutors but also uses peer tutoring methods. Often, the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung holds job guidance training collaborating with other partners who also bring their own tutors. However, if there is no collaboration with partners or third parties, job guidance is carried out using peer tutors.

5. Obstacles and Solutions

To support the success of job guidance program activities, adequate infrastructure is needed. In this case, the existing facilities and infrastructure at the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung for the job guidance program implementing needs improvements.

One of which is limited land that inhibits the existing job guidance program implementation. Other inhibiting factors are costs and technical personnel. In one year, the government only funds two job guidance programs, where the programs should occur annually. Meanwhile, the job guidance training fails to meet the needs of each job post.

Technicians are also one of the limiting factors since the costs provided are less than the existing needs, and thus affecting technicians. Often the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung is confused about holding a job guidance training program due to the limited costs. Therefore, there is a need for volunteering partners or third parties to provide job guidance programs for inmates.

It is typical for the inmates to become one of the inhibiting factors since their interests and talents are different. Some job posts might be empty of enthusiasts, which can hamper the process of implementing the existing job guidance program.

The Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung always monitors and evaluates the job guidance development program to find solutions to any existing obstacles and improve the program.

6. Inmate Conditions

Independence guidance in the job guidance activities at the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung is very beneficial for their mental, physical, and skill development. The interview results with four inmates revealed that each of them took part in different job guidance activities. Each selected a job post that suits their interests, talents, and previous skills. They have participated in job guidance activities since the beginning of their sentence at the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung.

The inmates really enjoyed the job guidance activities, where two out of four interviewed inmates revealed that they experienced no obstacles while participating in the activities. However, two inmates stated that the existing facilities and infrastructure were one of the obstacles. For example, at the bakery job post, it was suggested that facilities and infrastructure must be improved further.

Having abundant orders and the need for a fairly large space with inadequate facilities and infrastructure was one of the obstacles felt. Furthermore, the hydroponic job post also showed that if there are other ongoing activities, they have no time to check the plants they are planting, while hydroponic plants, particularly their water content, must have the utmost concern.

The inmates wish to be given time to check the plants they are planting although other activities are running. Inmates asserted that job guidance activities had many positive impacts for them even though they were serving their sentences. Some of the impacts are time is flying by and days are filled with fruitful things to improve their independence.

They receive a lot of knowledge and experience while participating in existing job guidance activities. Following the effect expected by the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung, inmates will have useful skills after they complete their sentence. It is felt by the inmates and the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung, where inmates have abilities and skills to produce services and goods such as bread and snack boxes, the flagship programs at the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

1. Conclusions

Based on the study results concerning Job Guidance Management for Inmates in Cultivating Empowerment and Independence (Descriptive Study in Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung), the following conclusions can be drawn:

- a. Job guidance training must be followed by all inmates by following several stages before entering the job post, i.e., identification, assessment, training, and job post.
- b. Job guidance training aims to form independent individuals because they have the skills to return to society and can create jobs after being released from prison.

- c. Job guidance activities at Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung are divided into 3 types: Manufacturing, Services, and Agribusiness, which are then subdivided into 12 job posts. The total number of inmates participating in job posts until April 2024 is 166 people.
- d. The obstacles in implementing job guidance are infrastructure, costs, and technical personnel.

2. Recommendations

These recommendations are made by researchers as input and consideration aimed at:

a. Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung

For the Female Penitentiary Class IIA Bandung, the study results can be used as a reference for correctional institutions to develop job guidance management to improve the quality and effectiveness of its implementation; hence, the program's objectives of empowering and fostering the independence of inmates can be achieved according to the predetermined institution's targets.

b. Inmates

It is expected for inmates to take part in job guidance activities that are carried out as well as possible. After the inmates are released, they will have the skills and independence to continue as a business opportunity.

c. Researchers

For future researchers, this research can be used as reference material for other parties or researchers who want to research further regarding the same issue. It is hoped that future researchers can develop this research by focusing more on the problems studied and increasing literature studies and the data completeness.

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